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REPRODUCTIVE HEALTH AS SPECIE OF HUMAN RIGHT IN INTERNATIONAL LAW

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Abstract

Reproductive health is a human right as well as ecological right. These rights are guaranteed through various International Instruments as well as local legislations. Prominent among these International Instruments are the International Covenant on Economic Social and Cultural Rights, Convention for the Elimination of all forms of Discrimination against Women, American Convention on Human Right, the African Charter on Human and People's Right and etcetera. Reproductive health has constituted a serial problem in the global community, apparently due to ignorance on the efficacy of the genius 'human rights' as well as 'religion-cultural' inclinations and practices. It is observed that both males and females are victims of the reproductive failures which made them sad. The regime of Assisted Reproductive Technology has been a welcome development in rescuing the plights of childlessness in most couples. However, some religious practices remain vehemently opposed to the available remedies ushered by technology, which is perceived as a misnomer to natural conception. The author argued that legislative provisions of state parties be made compulsorily available to the citizenry in order to set them free from religious and cultural bondages opposed to alternative means of procreation. The paper therefore maintained that environmental degradation has in some cases operated to hamper reproductive health in some nations inclusive of Nigeria. The author therefore concluded that absolute precautions are to be accommodated in order to preserve national biodiversity and eco system.

Keywords: reproductive health, human right, religious and cultural practices, procreation, infertility

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1. Introduction

Reproductive right came into being when the earth was created. This right predates human existence with reference to the book of Genesis.¹ It is the will of the Creator that all creations should reproduce inclusive of all Animals, Birds, Fishes, Trees, and etcetera. It was recorded in the Holy Book that ‘God bless them saying be fruitful, and multiply and fill the waters in the seas and let fowl multiply in the earth.’²

The Biblical account was that, human being³ was last in God’s creation, yet it was the will of God that humans should multiply on the surface of the earth to take stewardship⁴ of all living creatures. It is one record that the first woman on earth was Eve, she was a reproduction of Adam, in Biblical episode, a part of Adam’s body⁵ was extracted to form Eve and by this experiment, God started the process of reproduction scientifically. Reproduction was also seen when God vowed to destroyed the earth, however, he instructed Prophet Noah to carefully pick all living creatures in pairs to avoid extinction of any of the creatures at the end of the flood.⁶ God cursed and destroyed the entire world, but man was to serve as steward towards the preservation of reproduction, Reproductive rights are not solely for man, animals and other eco-system are included. Human rights is precarious in ecological desecration, therefore the eco-system must be preserved.

The World Health Organisation⁷ defines reproductive rights as the rights which encompass the basic right of all couples and individuals to decide freely and responsibly the number, spacing and timing of their children and to have the information and mean to do so, and the right to attain the highest standard of sexual and reproductive health. They also include the right of all to make decisions concerning reproduction free of discrimination, coercion and violence.⁸ By implication the definition includes the following:

- i. The right to legal and safe abortion.
- ii. The right to birth control and freedom from coerced sterilization abortion and contraception.
- iii. The right to access good quality reproductive health care.
- iv. The right to education and access to free and informed reproductive choice.

¹ Genesis 1: New International version Bible.

² Ibid.

³ Genesis 1:26

⁴ Genesis 1:28

⁵ Genesis 2:21-22

⁶ Genesis 6:20-

⁷ [Hereafter, The WHO]

⁸ Nkolika Ijeoma Aniekwu, Reproductive Health Law: A Jurisprudential Analysis of Gender Specific Human Rights for the African Region, 1st ed., Ambik Press Nigeria, P.15

- v. The right to receive education about sexually transmitted infections and other aspects of sexuality and protection from gender based practices etc.

The highest attainment of any human being is to live in good health. It is the greatest wealth that has been bestowed on mankind. Reproductive health recognition has gathered momentum in various legislations including International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Right,⁹ International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights,¹⁰ European Convention on Human Rights,¹¹ African Charter on Human and Peoples Right.¹²

Lately the concept of reproduction health being a focus in human rights, have been accommodated in several international conferences, aimed at promoting the programme by creating awareness and monitoring the progress made. The international conference on population and development¹³ was held in Cairo, Egypt 1994. The conference made reference to its chapter VII, recognizing reproductive health as the right to dignity privacy, health and freedom from Discrimination on Gender basis.

The ICPD programme specifically touched also on issues bothering the all-round fitness of man and woman as it concerns reproduction. In defining reproductive health, the ICPD states as follows:

A state of complete physical, mental and social wellbeing and not merely the absence of disease or infirmity, in all matters relating to the reproductive system and its functioning and processes.

Reproductive health therefore implies that people are able to have a satisfying and safe sex life and that they have the capacity to reproduce and the freedom to decide if, when and how often to do so... the right of men and women to be informed and to have access to safe, effective affordable and acceptable methods of family planning of their choice as well as other methods if appropriate health-care services that will enable women to go safely through pregnancy and child birth services and provide couples the best chance of rearing a healthy infant”.

2. Framework on Reproductive health care

There are many and varied instruments appertaining to reproductive health. They include:

I. Universal Declaration of Human Rights 1948

This is one of the instruments that recognised the right to Reproduction as Human Rights. It states that:

⁹ ICESCR (1966) UN Doc A/6316

¹⁰ Ibid

¹¹ UN Treaty Series 213 (New York: UN, 1959), 221

¹² Organisation of African Unity, ACHPR, OAU 1981 Doc Cab/67/3/Rev 5

¹³ [Hereafter, The ICPD 1994] The ICPD was part of Resolution 49/28 of the United Nation General Assembly as endorsed

Everyone has the right to a standard of living adequate for the health and wellbeing of himself and of his family including food, clothing, housing, medical care, necessary social services and the right to security in the event of employment, sickness, disability, widowhood, old age or other lack of livelihood circumstances beyond his control¹⁴ children born outside wedlock are inclusive of this gesture.

II. International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights

This is another instrument embracing the tenets of reproductive rights as specie of human rights. This instrument came to force in 1966, it provided that the right to attain the highest level of wellness must not be denied from anyone. It also provided that:

- i. There must be a reduction of still-birth-rate of infant mortality and for the healthy development of the child.
- ii. There must be a condition which would ensure that medical services are available to the sick, even during emergencies.

The committee on Economic, Social and Cultural Right recognised that the right to health is interdependent on other human rights including good Eco-friendly Environment, Food, Housing, Education and the enjoyment of other benefits from scientific exports, Equality, prohibition of Torture, Privacy, access to Information, Freedom of association and freedom of movement. The committee further ensured that the right to good health is primarily anchored on access to good environment.¹⁵

III. African Charter on Human and Peoples Right 1981

This charter realized the need to further expand the frontiers of human rights as a reproductive right by adding people's right to its charter. Realising that African continent being so distinct, and which housed the whole of 54 countries with different cultural background. The need to add people is unique to the charter by way of examining its tradition and customs to see how appropriate the goals of human rights can be achieved. Parts of its provisions include: 'Every individual shall have the right to enjoy the best attainable state of physical and mental health.'¹⁶

The diverse nature of African countries gave room to the charter for the emancipation of its people towards the realization of the goals that would undeniably place it at enviable standard in practice despite colonial legal autochthony on the continent. Therefore state parties shall take the necessary

¹⁴ Article 25, Universal Declaration of Human Rights 1948

¹⁵ ICESCR General Comment (14) the right to the highest attainable standard of health (Art 12) as adopted at the 22nd session of ICESCR Committee 11th August 2000. E/C 12/200014.

¹⁶ Article 16 (1) ACHPR

measure to protect the health of their people and to ensure that they received medical attention when they are sick.¹⁷

IV. Convention for the Elimination of Discrimination against Women¹⁸

This convention seems myopic and discriminatory in the protection of reproductive health right. The provision restricts itself to women gender. This instrument came on board in 1979 to protect women folk in the face of perceived discrimination against women in the field of employment in order to ensure basic equality with their male counterparts.

The provisions stated that: ‘State parties shall take appropriate measures to eliminate discrimination against women in the field of employment... and the right to protect the health and the safety in working conditions including safeguarding of the function of reproduction.’¹⁹

The convention further provided as follows: ‘The duty to fulfil these rights as provided the state parties are to take appropriate budgetary, economic and other measures to the maximum extent of their available resources to ensure that women realised their rights to health care.’²⁰

V. Convention on the Rights of the Child

This convention specifically seek to protect the right of every child against forced labour, sexual exploitation and gender based practices that undermine the integrity of the child, every child has a right to education, Free from cultural practices like girl child genital mutilation. (The practice of subjugating the girl child to harmful cultural practices are seen to be very frequent in most African societies and that there is a need to bridge the gap between the right enjoyed in other jurisdiction and the highly flaw rights tenable in many developing countries).

The convention also frown at underage marriages, for instance, a girl who has just attained puberty is ceremoniously given out to husbands, probably for the settlement of debts owed by her parents or for other reasons. The convention highly condemned the act of denying the girl child the necessary basic education, for instance, in some primitive societies, the girl child is never sent to school on the erroneous belief that, they were created solely for procreation. The convention recommend that state parties should ensure that a child, whether male or female be properly mentored into adulthood and be safe from force or hard labour and scavenging. This convention (the right of the child)²¹ was ratified in Nigeria in 1996. The convention admonished state parties to take all effective and

¹⁷ Article 16(2) ACHPR

¹⁸ [Hereafter, The CEDAW]

¹⁹ Ibid

²⁰ Ibid.

²¹ Resolution 44/25 of 20th November 1989, Entered into force 2nd September 1990 as ratified by 187 countries.

appropriate measures with a view to abolishing traditional practices prejudicial to the health of the child.

3. The interrelatedness between Human rights and reproductive health

Undoubtedly, human rights embraced reproductive right, for playing high premium on human wellbeing. Therefore all state parties are to ensure that these rights are placed on top priorities in their jurisdiction and to also discourage every act tantamount to the destruction of this right. The reproductive right of men and women must be respected in every jurisdiction, it takes two to tangle, a woman alone cannot reproduce; therefore men must also be protected from extinction. CEDAW particularly referred to the right of the women while other instruments at International and Regional levels recommend equal protection for both gender.

It is also the obligation of every state-party to fulfil all rights pivotal to the realization of this right as the right to health on humans are necessary for survival.

The CEDAW's general recommendation on women and health obliged state-parties with:

The obligation to respect rights requires states, parties to refrain from obstructing action taken by women in pursuit of their health goals. States parties should report on how public and private health care providers meet their duties to respect women's rights to have access to health care²²,

The Recommendation further emphasised the need for states to evaluate their laws or policies which mandate women to seek the authorization of their husbands, parents or health authorities before they can obtain health services, because such laws or policies are gender discriminatory and clearly a breach of their right to self-determination.²³ The recommendation further calls for duty to protect the rights required, and the 'promulgation and effective enforcement' of laws that forbid girl child marriage.²⁴ This includes an obligation to advance health care protocols and programs in gender enlightenment and training for providers of health care and in propagation of efficient health care services to aid in the to identification, tackling, prevention and remedies, against the causes of Women's ill health. The recommendation further enjoins, 'the duty to fulfil these rights places an obligation on states parties to take appropriate legislative, judicial, administrative, budgetary, economic and other measures to the maximum extent of their available resources to ensure that women realise their rights to health care.'²⁵

²² Art 12 CEDAW

²³ CEDAW General Recommendation on Women and Health, para 14

²⁴ Child Rights Act 2003 prohibits marriage for those below 18 years.

²⁵ See generally CEDAW provisions on child right.

The high rate of maternal deaths and pains, suffered by women is a manifestation that contravenes the right to access proper health care in vulnerable jurisdiction. In addition to these general obligations ICESCR has issued a General Comment that explains the minimum core obligations of Articles 12 on the right to the highest attainable standard of health. This General Comment establishes that states have core obligations to provide essential primary health care in or to satisfy the right to the highest attainable standard of health that the 'core obligations are not subject to resource limitations or progressive realization that their realization is required immediately.²⁶

There are Responsibilities on Governments in ensuring that Reproductive Health is attained by all:²⁷

- i. It is the responsibility of state parties to create an enabling environment where environmental laws interface with reproductive health care for the citizen on a non-discriminatory fashion.
- ii. To ensure that industrial activities which are inimical to health growth are discouraged especially from vulnerable populace, (industrial waste are health hazards in the form of pollution) which destroys not only man but other natural resources which man depend on for survival.
- iii. To ensure equitable distribution of all health facilities to the citizenry in sufficient quantity.
- iv. To adopt an action plan for addressing health and environmental concerns of the general population and to be monitored and review them periodically.
- v. To ensure reproductive material (pre-natal as well as post-natal) and child health care.
- vi. To provide education and access to information concerning the main health problems in the community including methods of preventing them.
- vii. To provide appropriate training for health personnel, including education on health and human rights.

The General Comment further expatiate obligations consequent on the protection of the right to health including banishing health related discrimination to health care. State parties are to take active and proactive measures towards health care. The choice of rights to apply will depend on the immediate and underlying causes of reproductive health issues arising.²⁸

Some of the specific rights, applicable and contributory to women's health generally, include:

- i. Rights relating to life, longevity, security and sex;
- ii. Rights on health care of women;

²⁶ CESCR General Comment No. 14; The Right to the Highest Attainable Standard of Health (Art. 12) Adopted at the Twenty-second Session of the Committee on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights, on 11 August 2000 (Contained in Document E/C.12/2000/4) <https://www.refworld.org/pdfid/4538838d0.pdf> Accessed 4 April 2025

²⁷ As provided by Article 12 of ICESCR

²⁸ Ibid.

- iii. Rights to non-discrimination;
- iv. Rights relating to reproductive choice.

The above agitation is determined by past application of these rights by National, Regional and International Human rights court(s) and tribunals;

- v. An identification of women's health issues that appear amenable to a human rights approach.²⁹

The success of individual and government efforts in applying human rights to reproductive and sexual health will vary in different circumstances and every effort will give rise to further emancipation towards positive directions on any foreseeable circumstances arising thereto with International standards.

4. Desiderata to fulfil the rights to Health³⁰

The United Nations Committee on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights (CESCR), General Comment No. 14 cited some key elements which are indispensable to the rights to health. These criteria are useful in the evaluation of the right to health.³¹

- i. Availability: Governments are to ensure that healthcare facilities are available in all sectors of the population. This requires that functioning public health and health-care facilities should be available and affordable in large quantity with compulsory annexation of National Health Insurance Scheme (NHIS) to everybody irrespective of status. Basic determinants of health must be present, such as potable water, adequate and trained medical personnel to executive the project³². Necessary drugs for all kinds of ailment are to be available and affordable as well.
- ii. Accessibility: The non-accessibility of health care has done damage to vulnerable population in its entirety therefore the committee mandate that health facilities, goods and services must not only be available, but must also be access to information about health – including access to information about sexual health.
 - (a) Non-discrimination: This should include the underlying determinants of health such as safe and portable drinking water and adequate sanitation facilities, hospital, clinic and other

²⁹ Ibid.

³⁰ Olaide Gbadamosi, "An Imperative for the Recognition of the Right to Health as a Fundamental Human Right in National Constitution" (2007-2009) Vol. 5-7, B.J.P.L 154.

³¹ CESCR General Comment No. 14: The Right to the Highest Attainable Standard of Health (Art. 12) Adopted at the Twenty-second Session of the Committee on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights, on 11 August 2000 (contained in Document E/C.12/2000/4) <https://www.refworld.org/pdfid/4538838d0.pdf> Accessed 4 April 2025.

³² Ibid.

health related buildings. Trained medical and professional personnel receiving domestically competitive salaries competitive of International standard³³.

- (b) Physical accessibility: Health facilities, goods and service must be accessible to all without discrimination.
- (c) Economic accessibility: Health facilities, goods and services must within safe physical reach for sections of the population especially vulnerable or marginalized groups such as ethnic minorities and indigenous population, women, children, adolescents', older person with disability and persons living with HIV/AIDS.
- iii. Acceptability: Acceptable health care services are necessity to ethical standards to Doctors and other Medical practitioners. All health facilities, goods and services must be respectful of medical ethic and culture sensitive to gender and life-cycle requirements confidentially to improve the health status of those concerned.³⁴
- iv. Quality: All medical facilities and services are to be in good standard in adherence to ethical procedures appropriately. Health facilities must be adequate in portable water and sanitation services, scientifically approved drugs and equipment as well as skilled medical personnel.³⁵

A. Men Reproductive Healthcare

Reproductive health is not only for women, men are also endangered species of reproductive health hazard. The required revolution care can be worthwhile if both Men and Women enjoy the same benefits of reproductive health.

Some common issues affecting men reproductive system are:

- i. Prostrate
- ii. Varicocele
- iii. Erectile dysfunction
- iv. Hormonal imbalances
- v. Poor ejaculation
- vi. Low sperm count
- vii. Pains swelling as lump in the testicle area
- viii. Decrease facial or body hair, (a sign of chromosomal or hormonal abnormalities
Other epididymitis inflammation and etcetera³⁶

³³ ibid

³⁴ Ibid

³⁵ Nkolika Ijeoma Aniekwu, supra

³⁶ Mayoclinic <<https://mayoclinic.org>>

The above listed could hamper greatly the effectiveness of male reproductive circle leading to infertility in men. Men reproductive organs are a key portion that influences women reproductive health and great priority to be given to men health status for the overall wellness of the citizens. The instrument for human right at National and International levels recognised reproductive health successes of men and women as a right that must be enjoyed together. Until men are accessible to medical cares for instance, the labour on women reproduction might end up in vain.

5. Reproductive health in International law and human right

The practice of female genital mutilation impacts negatively on the regime of human right. It is an abuse on humanity and this evil is highly practiced in many societies and less developed economies. This practice has resulted in excessive complication in women health as well as psychological tumour in womanhood. The ignorance associated with this practice is massive notwithstanding the justifying claims that circumcision reduced promiscuity in women. The claim has been severally discredited by scientific research, rather mutilation of the genital lead to severe pains, genital ulcerations, recto vaginal fistula (RVF).³⁷

Female genital mutilation is a gross breach of human right, in that it violates the right of dignity of man in its entirety Sec 34 of the Nigeria Constitution 1999 (as amended) states: ‘No person shall be subjected to torture or to inhuman or degrading treatment.’³⁸

The provisions of CEDAW also frown at inhuman treatment of the human person. CEDAW admonished state parties to protect women from harmful traditional practices capable of endangering the women folk. It condemned the act of female circumcision.³⁹ The covenant on civil and political rights ICCPR also state that: ‘No one shall be subjected to torture or to cruel inhuman or degrading treatment or punishment.’⁴⁰

The indiscriminate tampering with female genitals could affect the reproduction organs in women which is capable of hampering proper and dignifying condition of living.

There is also in existence another factor associated with reproductive health issue. Recall that certain cultures in African societies encourage child betrothal and early marriage. Young girls are betrothed

³⁷See Generally, T.C Okeke, et al An Overview of Female Genital Mutilation in Nigeria. <<https://www.nebi.nm.nih.gov/pmcarticles/pmc3507121>> Accessed 10/4/25

³⁸ See 34 (1a) 1999 Constitution (as amended)

³⁹ See No. 19 of CEDAW recommendations.

⁴⁰ See Article 7 of (ICCPR)

to young boys or to older men, sometimes as early as infant. Such a betrothed girl is expected to become the wife of the man to whom she was betrothed as soon as she reaches puberty. At times, the girls are not betrothed, but are out-rightly married off to men completely against their wish. The rights of such a child-wife are abused by her family and the so called husband.

The early sexual activities and child bearing are characterized by multiple gynaecological problems, some of which include labour complications resulting in maternal death, Vesico-vaginal Fistula (VVF) and collapsed uterus. The very pathetic aspect of the problem is that the girls who suffer from VVF, which is characterized by foul odour emanating from the urine and faeces which constantly leaks out, are abandoned after a while by the so called husband and ending up being ostracized by the family and society.⁴¹

The issues of marriageable age, consent and early child or under aged marriages have human rights implication on the family and private lives, especially for women. The right to marry and to find a family is available to persons of 'marriageable age'. In Nigeria for example, 18 years is the minimum marriageable age prescribed for both genders by the National Policy on Population. It should be noted that customary practices regarding marriage of many young girls subsists, as customary law practices itself is subject to geographical spatial relation.⁴² However, the regime of human rights take accommodates maturity and consent of any person to go into a relationship of marital status.

Flowing from the above, the burden falls on state authority to ensure that entry into marriage relationships conforms to human rights standards concerning voluntary choice to marry. The Committee on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights (CESCR), in its concluding observations on its report recommended that 'the laws that permit persons to marry without the acknowledgement or consent of the partner be abolished.' In its concluding observations on the report on Cameroon, CESCR also deplored 'the lack of progress made by the Government combating early marriage of their girls. CEDAW's General Recommendation on Equality in marriage and Family Relations, observed in Article 16(1) (a) and (b) as follows: 'A woman's right to choose a spouse and enter freely into marriage is central to her life and to her dignity and equality as a human being.'

⁴¹ Jane Muthumbi, Joar Svanemyr, Elisa Scolaro, et al (2015) Female Genital Mutilation: A Literature Review of the Current Status of Legislation and Policies in 27 African Countries and Yemen. African Journal of Reproductive Health, September 2015; 19(3); 34.

⁴² Odiaka Ngozi Oluchukwu, "Women's Rights in Nigeria: What's Holding Nigeria's Women Back?" <https://www.worldpoliticsreview.com/insights/20822/womens-rights-in-nigeria-what-s-holding-nigeria-s-women-back> accessed 10/3/25.

Sexually transmitted disease is another aspect of menace that has badly affected the reproductive system of both men and female and it has made life precarious for humanity. The ICCPR which is a covenant assuring the certainty of life described life as inherent, and therefore, should be protected by law. Human right protection is a necessity in every legislation, requiring each state parties to ensure its preservation. HIV and AIDS infection in human has had adverse effect on reproductive health of nations especially those with low income capacities.

It is the responsibilities of state parties to care for those infected by this pandemic and be free from dehumanization and stigmatization. It is however on records that some nations has made adequate provision to check this scourge Venezuela⁴³. Some African nations like Tanzanian and Nigeria have also embarked on propaganda and enlightenment on the need to stop discrimination against those living with HIV and AIDS as well as some precautionary measures to check these menaces as well as other sexually transmitted diseases.

It is the view of many African countries, especially the highly infested ones that victims have the right to reproductive health care as well as the right to life in accordance to the ratifications of various international conventions they have entered into.

The issue of Abortion cannot be over-emphasized. This is a critical aspect of human right analysis, many religious bodies and the conservative frown at the practice of abortion in whatever circumstance. They viewed abortion as the taking of innocent lives, and the unlawful denial of the innocent souls to be born and that this act is against humanity and God, the maker of lives. However, the African charter conference 2003 also known as Maputo Protocol explicitly addressed the issue of abortion as it relates to reproductive health right and human rights.

The protocol required state parties to protect the reproductive health right of women by authorizing medical abortion in the following cases of sexual assault like rape, incest and etcetera, and to save the life of the woman where her health is endangered by any pregnancy, every other reasons outside the safety of the mother was not address lightly by the protocol⁴⁴. An area of serious concern has been whether the restriction of law prevents women right to freedom is highly debatable within international law, where freedom was an element and core idea of the exercise. In most advance nations like the European Union and UK, and etcetera, there has been less restriction on women's right to abortion provided it is safe for the general good of her health. However, contrary to the views of the developed nations, the African nations though bound by traditional belief and religion,

⁴³ In the case of Paschim Samity v. State of West Bengal (1996) 4 Sec 37.

⁴⁴ Maputo protocol 2003. Accessed through int Justice Centre <https://isrcenter.org/themotic/researchguide/women-human-rights/> accessed 4/4/25.

like South-Africa and nations within her neighbourhood like Zambia, are liberal with legal abortion as long as procedures are followed.⁴⁵ But in 1996, South Africa enacted the Choice on Termination of Pregnancy Act, making it abortion law one of the most liberal in the world. The Act permits abortion without limitations during the first 12 weeks of pregnancy, within 20 weeks on numerous rounds and at any time if there is risk to the women's life or of severe fatal impairment. The Act repealed a 1975 law that had prohibited abortion unless the pregnancy as a result of rape or incest, the mother's life was in danger, or there was a fatal impairment.⁴⁶

In 1996, Burkina Faso amended its Penal Code to permit abortion at any state of pregnancy when a woman's life or health is endangered and in the case of severe foetal impairment. Abortion is also permitted during the first 10 weeks of pregnancy in cases of rape or incest. Under the previous law, abortion was prohibited unless perform to save a woman's life. In other African nations like Egypt, the criminal law makes no explicit exception to protect life and has been interpreted to permit abortion under such circumstances on the grounds of 'necessity'.

In Zambia, the law permits abortions on 'social and economic grounds' but receives broad interpretations as medical personnel are typically allowed to consider a woman's economic resources, her age, marital status and the number of her living children. In other countries, abortion is strictly prohibited or permitted only to save the woman's life'. In Zimbabwe the threatened injury to the woman's health must be either 'serious or permanent'. In Senegal, the criminal law prohibits abortions and makes no explicit exception to protect life, even though it has been interpreted to permit abortion on the ground of necessity⁴⁷.

However, abortion is still criminalized in Nigeria except when the life of a woman is at risk. In some northern regions of the country, where sharia law is widespread, abortion services are not accessible at all. Administrative barriers, coupled with widespread patriarchal beliefs and practices, make access to abortion extremely limited for women, and even more out of reach for girls. To procure a legal abortion, a woman must obtain permission from a physician and a gynaecologist, and many times providers demand consent from her husband too, and the refusal to grant consent will leave the women with no option than to keep the foetus which could lead to maternal mortality.

Domestic violence is another critical issue. Domestic violence in many developing nations has been occurring at an alarming rate. Though this phenomenon is global and usually leaving its victims in utter disappointments and frustration. In some cases domestic violence has led to casualties of high

⁴⁵ Centre for Reproductive rights. The World Abortion Laws <<https://reproductive.rights.org/map/world-Abortion-law>>. Accessed 5/4/25.

⁴⁶ Ibid

⁴⁷ Ibid

and mild proportion. This violence involved not only women, but men inclusive. But men and women worldwide has suffered the tortured associated with domestic violence to include their inability to fully enjoyed the right to reproductive health.

Domestic violence violates the essential elements of human rights. There has been large campaign against this scourge since the world conference on human rights was held in Vienna in 1993, civil society and groups has acknowledge that violence against women is an aberration to public policy and human right concerns.⁴⁸ Issues that were stressed in the conference include the following:

- i. Strict adherence to women reproductive rights by state parties
- ii. Social justice for vulnerable women who are victims of the evils associated with domestic violence,
- iii. Stop the exploitation of women through harassment, trafficking⁴⁹ force and underage marriage,
- iv. Genital female mutilation and other cruel practices associated with women's right violations were out rightly criticised and condemned.

Domestic violence has hampered the right to reproductive health care and human rights in no small ways in men, there were instances where the male genital were violently cut off by their spouses and sometimes killed by their female counterparts as well.

The recommendation of the human right committee HRC, stressed the need for equality of right between men and female⁵⁰, state parties are obligated to treat men and women equally in marriage.

Mention should also be made of Eco-System, A Propellant to Reproductive Healthcare. Biodiversity has important role in the conservation of the eco-system which is crucial to human survival. The eco-system focuses on how living organisms interact with each other in the environment thereby, forming self-sustainable system, for example, fishes and other aquatic plants, water' sunlight and micro-organism form part of human existence. Plants breathe in carbon dioxide and breathe out oxygen which is crucial for man's survival. The quality of life is a major determinant to reproductive health of all mammals including man. In Nigeria for instance, desertification has hampered the growth of the forest, giving room to climate hazards, Nigeria relies so much on biodiversity for her tremendous population, biodiversity provides more than half of the population's

⁴⁸ World Health Organisation. Multi Country Study on Women's health and domestic violence against women, held in Vienna 1993.

⁴⁹ Article 38 Vienna declaration and programme of action

⁵⁰ See Generally HRC General Comment 28

food requirement⁵¹. More than half of the population relies on terrestrial and aquatic resources of the Niger River Basin.⁵² This biodiversity and food are connected and inseparable, therefore biodiversity of the forest, marine and wetland resources provide an environment conducive for reproductive health in Nigeria and world over. There is an urgent need to conserve the environment against greenhouse gas emission, and other threat to species invasion in the eco-system through environmental regulatory agencies such as NESREA, and etcetera.

There is also Assisted Reproductive Technology (ART). There is a rapid advancement in the Assisted Reproductive Technology in the world recently. This system takes the form of In Vitro Fertilization (IVF) Pre-implantation Genetic Testing, Surrogacy, Gamete Intra-Fallopian transfer and etcetera.⁵³ This procedure has secured the successes of married couple who are seen to be infertile. Assisted Reproductive Technology has not been given worldwide recognition by legislation especially the less developed societies who nevertheless practice it. The proponent for ART prohibition believed that the system is capable of causing harm to the society and that the system is capable of impeding the human reproductive process as it is against the already established legal norms regarding reproduction, that ART is an illegal process and practice.⁵⁴ On a contrary argument, ART is viewed as a human right, which is a right to reproduction and reproductive liberty. The ART processes and practice is a personal choice and a person have the right to determine his social status and the choice of ART as a social status that must not be interfered into by anybody or organisation or regulated by any measure. According to Robertson,⁵⁵ the right to conception, Bearing and Parentage of children are personal choices that must be protected by the state whether or not they are exercised through natural or artificial means. Therefore, the state is under obligation to make sure that ART choice are protected provided the system satisfies the biological social, cultural and psychological need of the individuals⁵⁶. States like Australia has a federal regulatory framework through the National Health and Medical Research Council

⁵¹ S. Allen NFNFR, Nigeria: Fifth National Biodiversity Report, 2015

⁵² AFDB, African Development Bank Group: (Programme for Integrated Development and Adaptation to Climate Change in the Niger Basin 2018). <<https://www.afdb.org/en/documents/mutinationalprogramme-forintegrateddevelopmentandadaptation.appraisal-report109273>>. Accessed 5/4/25.

⁵³ Francis Fukuyama, Our Post-human Future: Consequence of the Biotechnology Revolution (New York: Farrar Straux Giroux (2002), 5.

⁵⁴ This is the position held by religious bodies including Islam, claiming that the practice tampered with human embryos for pregnancy is against Allah's will. Quran chapter 2 verse 223.

⁵⁵ John Robertson; Children of choice: Freedom and the New Reproductive Technologies (Princeton University press) 1994, 39.

⁵⁶ Ibid.

(NHMRC).⁵⁷ Furthermore, the Australian medical council founded the ART on the following principles:

- (a) That ART procedures are carried out in such a manner that respects the rights and interests of all participants.
- (b) That the health and interest of any children delivered through ART must be given utmost priority in the utilisation of these technologies.
- (c) That these technologies should be applied in such a way as to minimize harm and maximize the potential of intended parents or couples who are involved.
- (d) That the process of decision-making about ART must take into consideration the genetic linkage and social relationship that may result from their application.
- (e) That the process of determining eligibility criteria for ART is just, transparent, and equitable and conforms with human rights standards including the right to freedom from discrimination.
- (f) The application of ART must be based on an effective legal framework that tends to reduce interventions that are not premised on evidence and clinical results⁵⁸.

6. Conclusion

From the beginning of the world God has placed great premium on human existence. It is the will of God that every living creature should multiply including human being. Multiplication is a right for all and this reproductive health cut across the globe, reproductive system could either be natural i.e. through conception or artificial by the use of IVF and other technological assisted methods. Reproductive right is recognised through various International treaties and conventions, and provides for the protection of reproductive health of the individuals.

We also maintained that human beings (either male or female) have the right to be protected against abuse and violation of his Productive health practices. A number of International instruments has been domesticated into local legislation for the protection of these rights, though poorly implemented in many developing economies. A nation free from barrier to reproductive health is advocated to protect reproductive rights in humanity.

⁵⁷ National Health and Medical Research Council (NHMRC) Ethical Guidelines on the ART in Clinical Practice and Research: Working to Build a Healthy Australia, 2017

⁵⁸ Ibid., para. 2.

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